

MANAGEMENT AND COORDINATION OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS BASED ON PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP

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ABSTRACT

preschool education is one of the important stages in children's lives. In Uzbekistan, preschool educational institutions under public-private partnership (PPP) are one of the main sectors that help children's early development. This article highlights important aspects of coordinating and managing the educational activities of preschool educational institutions under public-private partnership.

In global practice, ensuring the comprehensive development of children—strengthening their health, supporting their social-emotional growth, fostering intellectual and creative abilities, and maintaining physical and psychological stability—has been recognized by the United Nations as a pressing task within the Sustainable Development Goals set for 2030. Specifically, the goal of “ensuring early childhood development, care, and access to pre-primary education” has been highlighted as a priority. To achieve effectiveness in the education system, the trend is toward creating flexible educational models and alternative methods of preparing children for school. This process necessitates the introduction of mechanisms for the effective management of preschool education institutions.

In developed countries, various models of establishing non-state preschool education institutions—particularly those based on public-private partnerships—are widely applied. Scientific and practical research is being conducted on issues such as establishing state-private partner relations in managing and regulating the activities of non-state preschool institutions, introducing digital technologies into management processes, applying mechanisms of public oversight to preschool education management, improving horizontal and vertical management, evaluating management activities, and developing algorithmic calculations for management processes.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has been implementing reforms aimed at introducing state educational standards and curricula based on modern requirements for effective education, upbringing, and early development of infants and preschool-aged children into the preschool education system. For example, through the development and improvement of regulatory and legal documents, opportunities have been created for the growth of the non-state sector in

this field. In particular, the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4312 dated May 8, 2019, approving the "Concept for the Development of the Preschool Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030," identified important priority areas such as improving the management system of preschool education, introducing entirely new approaches to the training, retraining, professional development, selection, and advancement of personnel in the preschool education system.

In this regard, improving the management mechanisms of non-state preschool education institutions established on the basis of public-private partnerships, applying management functions in practice, introducing systems for managing education quality, and evaluating management efficiency are considered urgent directions.

Furthermore, the Presidential Decrees of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3651 dated April 5, 2018 "On measures to further encourage and develop the preschool education system," No. PQ-3955 dated September 30, 2018 "On measures to improve the management of the preschool education system," and No. PQ-5144 dated June 10, 2021 "On additional measures to expand the network of preschool education institutions in districts with low coverage rates," as well as other regulatory and legal documents related to this sector, serve as a framework for implementing the tasks outlined. This research contributes to the realization of these objectives to a certain extent.

By Resolution No. 426 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 2, 2022, "On measures to simplify public-private partnership relations in the field of preschool education through modern digital technologies," amendments were introduced regarding the payment of subsidies from the state budget to preschool education institutions based on public-private partnerships, maintaining staff and student attendance records through an electronic application, and procedures for paying staff salaries from state budget funds.

Looking at international experience, public-private partnership relations in the preschool education system are widely implemented. For example, in Kazakhstan's preschool education system, in recent years significant attention has been given to the private sector and public-private partnerships. Among the measures taken are the introduction of per-child financing and the abolition of mandatory licenses for operating in this sector. It is also recognized that easing sanitary-hygienic requirements and construction standards for preschool institutions has significantly increased children's enrollment in preschool education in that country.

Analysis of educational practice highlights the necessity of correctly applying management functions in non-state preschool education institutions based on public-private partnerships, establishing education quality management as the main direction of institutional activity, and developing criteria for evaluating management efficiency.

List of References:

1. Resolution No. 83 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 12, 2025, "On additional measures for increasing the coverage of children with preschool education in 2025-2026"
2. Resolution No. PQ-403 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 22, 2024, "On additional measures to increase private sector participation in the field of education."
3. Resolution No. 426 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 02, 2022, "On measures to simplify public-private partnership relations in the field of preschool education through modern digital technologies."
4. Resolution No. PQ-3651 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved on April 5, 2018, "On measures to further encourage and develop the system of the Ministry of Preschool and School Education."